

SPONTANEOUS SINGULARITIES AND GENERALIZED DYNAMICS OF NONLINEAR EQUATIONS OF MATHEMATICAL PHYSICS AND THEIR IMPLICATIONS FOR PHYSICS AND ASTROPHYSICS

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Abstract

- Vortons introduced to approximate finite core vortex tubes and pass through Navier Stokes spontaneous singularities/reconnections without any additional assumptions.
- Vortons provide “singular decomposition” of 3D vorticity field.
- Vortons have nonlocal 3D vorticity tails due to solenoid condition for vorticity. Superposition of vorticity in vorton chain produces finite core vortex tubes/filaments.
- They are not a weak solutions of Euler or Navier Stokes equations, being more flexible singularities designed to pass through NS “singular events” based on inviscid singular dissipation Refs.[1-8].
- Vortons provide irreducible description of inviscid attractor of 3D Navier Stokes equation solutions with number of vortons scaling with Reynolds number at hand.
- Magnetic vortons provide irreducible description of magnetic vortex tubes in plasma with reconnections without any additional assumptions.
- Instability of quasi 3D/2D+ vorton collapse provides possible mechanism for explosive universe inflation/first order phase transition.
- Positive feedback loop of quasi 3D vorton collapse and repulsive cosmological DCE.
- 3D space nature of our universe as a consequence of instability of 3D vortons collapse.
- “Dark matter” explained as a consequence of frisbee like quasi 3D/2D+ space in galaxies with corresponding stable rotational curves.
- “Dark energy” explained as a emergent result of vorton system 3D self amplification interaction energy “antigravity” effect.
- Probabilistic interpretation of quantum mechanics as a result of smooth test functions of fluid vacuum modified nonlinear Maxwell equations weak solutions.
- Baryon asymmetry explained as a instantaneous snapshot during exponential inflation of quark antiquark annihilation asymmetry/skewness and kurtosis terms in Edgeworth series expansion of instantaneous quantum GUP (generalized uncertainty principle) fluctuations.
- Quantum modified General Relativity QMOGER equations derivation physics proposed.
- Simple Early Bifurcation/Regime shift detection in nonequilibrium nonlinear statistical systems proposed using linear statistical moments/cumulants approximation/equivalents formulas.

Key Words: Vortons, solenoid dipole singularities, 3D turbulence, vortex reconnections, inviscid dissipation, Navier Stokes attractor, instability of 3D vorton collapse, universe inflation, dark matter, dark energy, 3D physical space, emergent antigravity, probabilistic interpretation of quantum mechanics, nonlinear Maxwell equations, baryon asymmetry,

Edgeworth series expansion, GUP generalized uncertainty principle, statistical moments, skewness and kurtosis, quantum modified General Relativity QMOGER .

SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION.

NAVIER-STOKES SOLUTIONS AND VORTON DYNAMICS.

The 3D Euler equations of incompressible inviscid fluid develop spontaneous singularities on timescales on the order of vortex rotations. Solutions to the 3D Navier-Stokes equations for incompressible viscous flow are smooth for all time, but they bifurcate and are not unique Ref.[1-8,29]. Interesting new results by Sasha Migdal indirectly prove that there is no blow up in Navier Stokes equations but there is “stochatization”, which may mean non uniqueness/bifurcations/branching of solutions. Plus his “quantization” probably means appearance of some elementary building blocks of 3D fully developed turbulence Refs.[63,64].

This all could be interpreted as indirect confirmation of old mathematics and physics conjectures about regularity/types of singularities of 3D Navier Stocks due to Leray, Kolmogorov and Onsager.

Vorton is introduced as the the simplest solenoid 3D vortex singularity Refs.[1-5,29]. Finite core vortex tubes may be represented as superposition of vortons Refs.[1-5]. Experimentally observed topological metamorphoses of vortex structures/reconnections could be seen in numerical vorton simulations without any additional assumptions. Vortons in plasma have magnetic dipole moments. Magnetic vorton tubes reconnect Refs.[1-5,14,29].

The 3D Navier-Stokes equations appear to have spontaneous singularities/reconnections and an inviscid vorton attractor that exhibits inviscid turbulence and dissipation Refs.[1- 5, 10,29] with corresponding Kolmogorov like energy cascade towards small scale.

Original reasons for introduction of vortons were to resolve the most important structures for description of fully developed 3D turbulence, 3D vortex finite core tubes/filaments Ref.(1-5,29), Eq.(1-5) and ability to pass through spontaneous singularities of Navier Stokes equations, which turn out to be bifurcations/branching of solutions/reconnections of vortex filaments/tubes.

Vorton is solenoid dipole 3D vorticity singularity. Velocity field generated by individual vorton.

$$v_i^{(\alpha)}(t, \mathbf{x}) = - \frac{\epsilon_{ijk} (x_j - x_j^{(\alpha)}) \gamma_k^{(\alpha)}}{4\pi |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^{(\alpha)}|^3}, \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_{ijk} is the unit antisymmetric tensor, and $x_j^{(\alpha)}(t)$ and $\gamma_k^{(\alpha)}(t)$ are the components of position and intensity, respectively, of the vorton labeled α .

Vorticity field of individual vorton. See solenoid dipole field picture fig.(19).

$$\Omega_i^{(\alpha)}(t, \mathbf{x}) = \gamma_i^{(\alpha)} \delta(\mathbf{r}^{(\alpha)}) + (4\pi)^{-1} \left(3r_i^{(\alpha)} r_k^{(\alpha)} \gamma_k^{(\alpha)} - |\mathbf{r}^{(\alpha)}|^2 \gamma_i^{(\alpha)} \right) |\mathbf{r}^{(\alpha)}|^{-5} \quad (2)$$

Where $\delta(\mathbf{r}^{(\alpha)})$ is a δ -function.

Even we start with vortons as a non solenoid delta functions of vorticity, still after we take curl of Biot Savart formula generated velocity vorticity field will be solenoid with closed vorticity lines see Eq.(2). Which obviously is non local 3D vorticity field due to solenoid condition.

Above fact turn out to be of importance for no need for regularization of vorton singularities which comes as a natural result from above nonlocal vorticity field.

And again vortons were not intended to be weak solutions of Euler or Navier Stokes equations, but a projection of 3D vorticity field on solenoid singular vorticity basis.

As a result it has enough flexibility to pass through reconnection event without additional assumption and without expensive necessity to resolve all possible 3D turbulence scales.

Vorton intensity change due to interaction with other vortons.

$$\dot{\gamma}_i^{(\alpha)} = \frac{\epsilon_{ijk}}{4\pi} \sum_{\beta} \left(r_{\alpha\beta}^{-3} \gamma_j^{(\alpha)} - 3r_{\alpha\beta}^{-5} r_j^{(\alpha\beta)} r_m^{(\alpha,\beta)} \gamma_m^{(\alpha)} \right) \gamma_k^{(\beta)}, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{r}_i^{(\alpha,\beta)} \equiv \mathbf{x}_i^{(\alpha)} - \mathbf{x}_i^{(\beta)}, \quad r_{\alpha\beta} \equiv |\mathbf{r}^{(\alpha,\beta)}|.$$

Vorton position change due to interaction with other vortons.

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(\alpha)} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \epsilon_{ijk} \sum_{\beta=1}^N r_{\alpha\beta}^{-1} \mathbf{n}_j^{(\alpha,\beta)} \gamma_k^{(\beta)}, \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}_i^{(\alpha,\beta)} &= \mathbf{x}_i^{(\alpha)} - \mathbf{x}_i^{(\beta)}, \\ r_{\alpha\beta} &= |\mathbf{r}^{(\alpha,\beta)}|, \\ \mathbf{n}_i^{(\alpha,\beta)} &= \mathbf{r}_i^{(\alpha,\beta)} r_{\alpha\beta}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Vorton's vorticity field, solenoid dipole. Vorticity and magnetic dipole fields Ref.(1-5,14).

Superposition of vorticity lines in 80 vortex ring.

Vortex tube clearly seen in a 80 vorton ring vorticity cross section . With vorticity cancelling out beyond it Refs.(3-5).

In fact we showed both analytically and numerically that chain of vortons approximates finite core vortex tubes with number of vortons corresponding to Reynolds number at hand Refs.(1-5), Fig.(1,2,19).

Another hope was that by introducing simplest solenoid vortex singularities which are analytically tractable we would be able to pass through some unknown NS "singular events" without any additional assumptions. Those events turn out to be vortex reconnections corresponding to bifurcations and branching of 3D NS solutions Ref.(1-5,29), Fig.(3-18). Both reasons appear to work out despite later vorton critiques, "modifications" and "improvements" Refs.(21-23).

Thus bifurcation and branching of Navier-Stokes solutions Refs.[6-9] can be interpreted as inviscid vorton reconnections Ref.(3-5). Very likely vortons describe dynamics on the Navier-Stokes attractor Ref.[9]. From a physical point of view vortons resolve the entire 3D vorticity field, which is superposition of 3D vortex tubes and is the only important aspect for

3D fully developed turbulence dynamics representation. And vortons showed ability to pass through NS “singular events” without any additional assumptions based on vortons inviscid dissipation ability Ref.(3-5,29).

We know from analysis Ref.[10] that the limit of a smooth sequence of functions may not be smooth. So even if Navier-Stokes solutions are all smooth, their inviscid limit could be singular. These singular inviscid solutions express the bifurcation of viscous solutions and finite dissipation rates. Rudin's math analysis book Ref.[10] says that limit of smooth sequence could be singular. So even if 3D NS solutions are smooth their limit/attractor could be singular/inviscid, especially if it explains all NS solutions dynamics without any additional assumptions and provide most economical/irreducible description of dynamics of 3D NS solutions for fully developed turbulence.

Hydrodynamics approach works for fluid vacuum modified Maxwell equations in inflation universe, turbulent plasma and for space-time dynamics with quantum entanglements.

SECTION 2: Vortex singularities and inviscid energy dissipation

Singular vortex dipoles, i.e. vortons, interact according to formulas Eq.(3,4),Ref.[1- 5]. As a consequence their amplitudes may self-amplify, a reflection of vortex stretching in three dimensions.

The interaction energy of vortons is given by Eq.(6),Ref.[1-5].

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{int}} = \frac{1}{8\pi} \sum_{\alpha < \beta} r_{\alpha\beta}^{-1} \left(\gamma_i^{(\alpha)} \gamma_i^{(\beta)} + \gamma_i^{(\alpha)} n_i^{(\alpha,\beta)} \gamma_j^{(\beta)} n_j^{(\alpha,\beta)} \right) \quad (5)$$

Interaction energy of vortons Refs.(2-5).

The self-energy of a single vorton is infinite, therefore it is not included in that formula. Due to the three dimensional stretching of vortons and self amplification, the interaction energy is not conserved. We may imagine that it goes into or comes out of the infinite self-energy of individual vortons Ref.[1- 5].

In the real world this corresponds to the fact that internal rotational degrees of freedom of 3D vortices are not resolved in the interaction energy formula. The stretching energy of vortex interactions may go into or out of unresolved rotational motions. Physically energy is dissipated at small scales by viscosity, but the precise amount is determined by inviscid dynamics.

The same phenomenon occurs in shock waves in compressible fluids, and also in magnetic field reconnection in the solar atmosphere. Dissipation provides the mechanism, but inviscid dynamics governs the behavior while viscosity, diffusivity, and resistivity play mop-up roles Ref.[16-18].

We performed numerical experiments with two vorton rings executing a “leapfrogging” cycle. The rings always self-destructed after 5 periods, regardless of the number of vortons in the rings.

Multiple reconnections then happened, with small rings appearing. During the destruction of the original rings we observed a negative spike in the vorton interaction energy, and a Kolmogorov-like energy power spectrum developed. This agrees with the physical

phenomena of energy transfer to small scales and inviscid dissipation of vorton interaction energy Eq.(5),

(6)

$$E_{\text{int}}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{2\pi^2} \sum_{\alpha, \beta} \left[\Phi_1(\mathbf{k}r_{\alpha\beta}) \gamma_i^{(\alpha)} \gamma_i^{(\beta)} + \Phi_2(\mathbf{k}r_{\alpha\beta}) \gamma_i^{(\alpha)} \mathbf{n}_i^{(\alpha, \beta)} \gamma_j^{(\beta)} \mathbf{n}_j^{(\alpha, \beta)} \right],$$

(7)

$$\Phi_1(z) = z^{-3}[(z^2 - 1) \sin z + z \cos z], \quad \Phi_2(z) = z^{-3}[(3 - z^2) \sin z - 3z \cos z]$$

Vortons interaction energy as a function of wave number Refs.(2-6).

Distance between two leapfrogging vorton rings. Self destroyed after almost 5 periods.

Energy spectrum of two leapfrogging vortex rings originally and at the moment of self distraction. Slope in log-log graph around -1.7. Plus negative spike in time derivative of interaction energy during distraction of the rings Ref.(2,3,5,29).

Recent experiments on colliding vortex rings show strikingly similar behavior, with large numbers of vortex reconnections and the appearance of multiple small rings Refs.[19].

SECTION 3: Magnetic vortons, hydrodynamics of turbulent plasma

The vorticity field of a vorton is identical in structure to the magnetic field of a magnetic dipole Fig.(19). In fact, in a turbulent plasma every vorton becomes magnetic due to the rotation of electrically charged plasma. So magnetic vortons interact both as a vorticity and magnetic dipoles Eq.(3,4,7).

Formula for force F between 2 magnetic dipoles \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_2 Ref.(14).

(7)

$$F = \frac{3\mu_0}{4\pi|r|^4} \{ (\hat{r} \times \mathbf{m}_1) \times \mathbf{m}_2 + (\hat{r} \times \mathbf{m}_2) \times \mathbf{m}_1 - 2\hat{r}(\mathbf{m}_1 \cdot \mathbf{m}_2) + 5\hat{r}[(\hat{r} \times \mathbf{m}_1) \cdot (\hat{r} \times \mathbf{m}_2)] \},$$

where μ_0 is the magnetic constant, \hat{r} is a unit vector parallel to the line joining the centers of the two dipoles, and $|r|$ is the distance between the centers of \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_2 .

Also, the magnetic amplitude and the vorticity amplitude will remain in a constant ratio, as they are stretched by the same fluid strain field. Formulas Eq.(3,4,7) describe the evolution of the magnetic vorton amplitude and their dipole-dipole interaction; note that there is no self-amplification of magnetic dipole momentum through magnetic interactions since the Maxwell equations are linear Ref.[14].

In section (3) we saw that chains of vortons provide an approximation of finite-core vortex tubes. Similarly, chains of magnetic dipoles provide an approximation of finite core magnetic flux tubes, as may be observed in the Sun or in nuclear fusion experiments. Inviscid dissipation associated with reconnection of magnetic vorton tubes may be the energy source for the very high temperatures on the surface of the Sun.

Our vorton horseshoe numerical experiments show reconnection and the expulsion of vortex rings.

Perturbed and unperturbed horseshoe vortex and it expelling vortex ring ref.(3-5).

These resemble the magnetic vortices that produce magnetic storms on Earth and disrupts magnetic confinement in plasma fusion experiments Ref.[16,17].

Appearance of magnetic vortons could be also understood based of equations for plasma turbulence similar to fluid modified Maxwell Equations with viscous dissipation added to equation 3.7 as a viscosity multiplied by Laplacian of velocity and singularities of Navier Stokes are less pronounced than in case of Euler equations (“singularities” here are branching/bifurcations of NS solutions/reconnections).

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{E}} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{B}} = 0 \quad (3.2)$$

$$\nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{E}} = -\frac{d\bar{\mathbf{B}}}{dt} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{B}} = \mu_0 \left(\bar{\mathbf{j}} + \epsilon_0 \frac{d\bar{\mathbf{E}}}{dt} \right) \quad (3.4)$$

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} = 0 \quad (3.5)$$

$$\frac{d\bar{\mathbf{j}}}{dt} = 0 \quad (3.6)$$

$$\frac{d\bar{\mathbf{V}}}{dt} = -\nabla \left[\frac{\alpha}{2} \left(\epsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{B^2}{\mu_0} \right) + \frac{g^2}{8\pi G} \right] \quad (3.7)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{V}} = 0 \quad (3.8)$$

Where in original Maxwell equations we substituted total/material/advective derivatives Refs. (37,29) instead of partial time derivatives and all the fields and charges are frozen in vacuum fluid and being advected.

And no need to transform corresponding equations into weak/integral form like will be necessary in equations of section 7. Notice that electromagnetism/plasma coupling constant equals 1 here in equation3.7.

SECTION 4: INSTABILITY OF VORTON COLLAPSE, UNIVERSE INFLATION AND “DARK MATTER”.

As we saw in articles Refs.[3-5,29,59] the system of 3 slightly non-parallel vortons almost perpendicular to 3 vortons plane (approximating 2D vortex dynamics) can start to collapse toward a point. Just before that collapse, however, 3D vorton self-amplification commences and leads to explosive vortons amplitudes and distances growth.

Jump in vorticity during 3 vorton collapse, LOG VORTICITY INTENSITY! against time Refs.(2,3,29). We have the same explosive grows in distances between vortons leading to space explosive inflationary grows and FIRST ORDER PHASE TRANSITION of vacuum compact dimensions to our quasi 3D world Refs.(2,3,29).

This could be a “turbulence” mechanism for the inflationary initial stage of the Universe expansion Refs.[15,29,59].

More precisely, imagine that the Universe starts as a point singularity fluctuation, and becomes a 2D or 3D turbulent fluid with gravity. In the 2D case gravity will collapse the Universe back to a singularity. However in 3D or quasi-3D/2D+* the vorton amplitudes and distances increase exponentially at the last stage of collapse, see Fig.(21) in Refs.[3-5,29]. Distances between vortons grow with growth of vorton intensities to prevent unlimited growth of interaction energy, thus providing “antigravity” effect. In fact vorton system nonlinear self amplification effect provide unique explosive mechanism for universe explosive expansion and “antigravity” effect.

This may explain why our world is 3 dimensional!

A quasi 3D frisbee-like world has 2 fully-developed dimensions and 1 short dimension; it might better be described as 2D+ or “frisbee-like”.

In 2D+ frisbee-like space the Universe may be slightly less complex, and have slightly more chances to fluctuate from the original singularity than a fully 3D Universe. And once gravitational collapse explodes in quasi 3D universe it will never get to any more complex spaces. Also quasi 3D/2D+ space may more naturally lead to explosive growth permitting closer vortons approach before 3D stretching and self amplification kicks in an explosive fashion. See Section 6 for positive feedback loop of quasi 3D vorton collapse and repulsive cosmological DCE.

However in 2D+/quasi 3D gravitational force decays proportionally to $1/r$ at a distances from the center of galaxy much larger than the short dimension, instead of $1/r^2$ as in 3D. A universe with two-plus dimensional structure could provide an alternative to “dark matter” as an explanation for anomalous rotation curves in galaxies. It has been observed in the edges of frisbee-like galaxies that star velocities do not depend on distance from the center. Explicitly, setting centripetal acceleration v^2/r equal to gravitational acceleration $\text{Constant} \cdot M/r$, we deduce that v must be constant in such a situation. This is a necessary condition for galactic disk stability Refs.[12,29,59].

Also Tully Fisher relation for galaxies could be deduced from 2D+ dimensional space in galaxies Ref.[67]. As a result we have luminosity and galaxy mass proportional to V^4 . And only baryonic matter necessary to explain all above observations including galactic rotational curves.

*2D+ universe space could be imagined as two commutative dimensions and third compact one non commutative with first two. In this case initially 2D vortex collapse will become locally 3D in a last moment due to generalized uncertainty principle GUP fluctuations Ref.(46). And explosive vortons self amplification/expansion/inflation will start at the point of collapse.

“Axes of Evil”/ hemispherical power anomaly Ref.(49) space asymmetry could be explained as confirmation of 2D+ nature of universe. In direction of short dimension we would have less stretching of space than in two larger dimensions directions and thus slightly larger temperature differences/gradients/variance.

SECTION 5. FLUID VACUUM MODIFIED NONLINEAR MAXWELL EQUATIONS

The wave functions of elementary particles are often interpreted as probability amplitudes. When they take the form of Gaussian distributions for isolated particle, they look very much like test functions for generalized solutions of unknown nonlinear equations.

Maxwell equations are linear and we don't expect any spontaneous singularities there starting with smooth initial conditions and thus no singular solutions expected there. However if by analogy to previous section 5 we assume original vacuum to be very dense and fluid (quark gluon plasma for example) we may modify Maxwell equations for fields and charges to be advected, frozen in fluid vacuum.

Thus we have following modified electromagnetism equations,

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (5.1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{B}} = 0 \quad (5.2)$$

$$\nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{E}} = -\frac{d\bar{\mathbf{B}}}{dt} \quad (5.3)$$

$$\nabla \times \bar{\mathbf{B}} = \mu_0 \left(\bar{\mathbf{j}} + \varepsilon_0 \frac{d\bar{\mathbf{E}}}{dt} \right) \quad (5.4)$$

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} = 0 \quad (5.5)$$

$$\frac{d\bar{\mathbf{j}}}{dt} = 0 \quad (5.6)$$

$$\frac{d\bar{\mathbf{v}}}{dt} = -\nabla \left[\frac{\alpha}{2} \left(\varepsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{B^2}{\mu_0} \right) + \frac{g^2}{8\pi G} \right] \quad (5.7)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{v}} = 0 \quad (5.8)$$

Where in original Maxwell equations we substituted total/material/advective derivatives Refs. (37,29) instead of partial time derivatives and all the fields and charges are frozen in vacuum fluid and being advected.

Vacuum itself satisfies incompressible Euler equation Refs.(37,29) (only transverse waves propagate there). And Euler equation (5.7) represents in right hand side gradient of energy density/dynamic pressure Refs.(36,37) of electromagnetic and gravity fields. And alpha is electromagnetism/vacuum coupling constant (around 1/173), which originally could have been closer to 1.

After instability/inflation/First order phase transition of vorton collapse created quasi 3D space out of original curled/compact vacuum dimensions we could observe that 3D Euler equation with vorticity develops spontaneous vortex like singularities Refs.(6-8) due to nonlinear stretching/self amplification on time scale of vortex rotation. Thus above nonlinear Maxwell equations transform into weak/integral form Ref.(32) with corresponding smooth test functions in order to pass through Euler equation singularity. As a consequence electromagnetic field and charges also become singular being subject to the same rate of strain as vorticity and being frozen into vacuum fluid.

As a final result we have singular/generalised solutions/"particles" with vorticity/spin and singular electric charge or electromagnetic field and with smooth test function distribution which squared could be interpreted as a probability density function.

Charged singularities with vorticity/angular momentum/spin and spatially distributed according to test function develop magnetic moment.

Here we have possible explanation of quantum mechanics properties of elementary particles. More details of actual elementary particles parameters are connected to influence of remaining compact vacuum dimensions with corresponding symmetries and entanglements and discrete nature of vacuum at the Planck scale.

SECTION 6. POSITIVE FEEDBACK LOOP OF QUASI 3D VORTON COLLAPSE DRIVEN UNIVERSE INFLATION AND REPULSIVE COSMOLOGICAL DCE.

In the case of 3D vorton collapse instability driven inflation we have a vortons turbulence trigger to start exponential space expansion with vortons frozen into space fabric and driving universe expansion with superluminal/supercausal speed.

Then we have quantum vacuum in newly created quasi 3D space which reacts to non adiabatic supercausal movement of Hubble horizon/boundary with quasi spherical geometry.

In this case known result is production of repulsive radiation energy/particles through dynamic Casimir effect/DCE Refs.[61,62].

In turn this energy pushing universe boundaries and stretching/amplifying vortons intensities, their interaction energy/"antigravity" and their numbers. Which then speeds up moving boundary and amplifies DCE energy/particles production. This positive feedback loop helps to explain explosive exponential universe inflation.

At some rather short time size of newly created space starts diluting interaction energy of vortons and DCE produced repulsive energy as a R^4 in case of radiation energy, thus slowing down moving universe boundary/ horizon.

At this point DCE changes from net energy producer/source to energy sink. And this is a start of universe reheating stage through use of inflation energy for matter production.

As a result we would essentially have the same CMB distribution as with inflaton model and only difference with starting mechanism/trigger based on 3D vortons collapse instability.

A possible consequence, current very small density cosmological constant energy could be partially explained by superluminal/supercausal expanding universe boundary, thus turning virtual particles into real particles/energy through cosmological DCE. **In particular when about 5B years ago universe switched to more fully 3D from quasi 3D cosmological DCE effect turned more repulsive, Ref.[29] as it is maximum in 3D spherical geometry.**

SECTION 7. GRAVITY AND 3D PHYSICAL SPACE AS A RESULT OF INSTABILITY OF 3D VORTON COLLAPSE /INFLATION

In approximately $10^{(-32)}$ sec original compact vacuum space exponentially inflated/expanded by a factor of at least $10^{(30)}$ into our current 3D physical space by mechanism of instability of quasi 3D/2D+ vorton collapse that was much faster than a speed of light Refs(41-43) and inflated space went beyond causality horizon of original vacuum space. Thus original compact vacuum space entanglements persisted in our current 3D space, possibly explaining gravity.

Baryon asymmetry Quark antiquark annihilation happens on $10^{(-25)}$ sec time scale and universe inflation happend on $10^{(-32)}$ sec time interval which probably explains some quark antiquark initial instantaneous imbalance at $10^{(-9)}$ baryons/photons ratio level Ref.(44).

And it could be explained similarly to CMB inhomogeneities as being inflation magnified instant GUP (generalized uncertainty principle) Ref.(46) Gaussian fluctuations of quark antiquark annihilations at the instant right before inflation commenced.

Due to instantaneous snapshot of Gaussian distribution at time scale of inflation $10^{(-32)}$ sec we may have instantaneous nonzero skewness and kurtosis moments/cumulants even at the normal fluctuations and appropriate coefficients in Edgeworth Series moments/cumulants expansion by statistical moments Ref.(45). It's next order to CMB Edgeworth expansion which is due to variance in Edgeworth Series, and could be seen in CMB fluctuations results at $10^{(-5)}$ level Ref.(45). Here first/variance term in Edgeworth expansion is cancelled because of quark and antiquark fluctuations both being normally distributed with equal variance.

SECTION 8: CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

Using “vortons”, i.e. discrete solenoid vortex dipole elements, essentially solves the problem of the most economical description 3D Navier Stokes equations and their solutions at Reynolds numbers above few thousands. Vortons irreducibly describe the physics of 3D vortex and magnetic vortex structures, providing dynamics on inviscid 3D Navier Stokes attractor scaling with corresponding Reynolds number. Instability/“inflation” of vorton collapse in quasi 3D space is proposed as an explanation of aspects of the origin of the Universe and phenomena attributed to “dark matter” and “dark energy” Refs.(29,39). Magnetic vortons provide dynamics of combined vortex and magnetic tubes in plasma including reconnections. No-slip boundary shown as a source of vorticity at the boundary and inside the flow. Plus in the process of self distraction of 2 leapfrogging vortex rings and subsequent reconnections we observed Kolmogorov like power law energy spectrum and energy cascade towards small scales.

In terms of cosmology results vorton system provides unique self amplification explosive nonlinear mechanism to explain early universe inflation/First order phase transition and current accelerated expansion with purely dimensional explanation of dark matter and dark energy without need for dark matter detection efforts. Also it explains results of MOND gravity theory, based on space dimensional structure, which similarly implicitly assumes $1/R$ gravity force in galaxies far from the center. And finally First order phase transition/inflation of original compact vacuum space to our quasi 3D physical space during universe explosive expansion leads to fluid vacuum induced appearance of spontaneous singularities in electromagnetism and weak/integral formulation which in turn explains appearance of elementary particles and their probabilistic distribution based on test function of generalized/weak solutions of fluid vacuum modified nonlinear Maxwell Equations. Spontaneous singularities in Navier Stokes and Euler equations lead to original smooth initial conditions turning into many body/“interacting singularities” problem.

A few ideas underpin this work:

3D Euler and Navier Stokes equations develop spontaneous singularities based on vorticity self-amplification. Note that the Euler equation requires transformation to weak/integral form to pass through the singularity.

Fluid vacuum or plasma are advected by 3D turbulence, and everything is locally subject to the same rate of strain as vorticity.

In the case of cosmological inflation, we have a time scale of **$10^{(-32)}$ sec**, which is much faster than any physical process time scale of fastest **$10^{(-25)}$ sec**. Instantaneous snapshots of these processes at inflation time scale could be very different from their typical results

due to GUP fluctuations asymmetries at that time scale.

There appears to be several interconnected events during exponential space inflation/first order phase transition. First it was instability of quasi 3D vorticity/vortons collapse driving universe expansion (much faster than the speed of light) with vorticity frozen into fabric of space while creating that space. That exponential inflation drove space far beyond causality horizon preserving original causal relationships, thus explaining resulting entanglements Ref(47,50,59). Again, these parts of space behave as original compact vacuum degrees of freedom through entanglements Refs.(29,47,50,59).

We can see that exponential inflation breaks several physics results if not physics laws per se. Plus hydrodynamics of quantum space-time introduces new covariant divergence term into original Einstein's general relativity equations, thus removing singularity of those equations and necessity of Big Bang.

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APPENDIX SECTION 1. Hydrodynamics of space-time, quantum modified general relativity.

Original physics explanations of derivation of quantum modified general relativity Qmoger equations in Refs.(51-56) are not very straightforward/compelling. On the other hand original derivation of Maxwell equations was based on some farfetched mechanical models. So as in many other cases equations turn out to be "smarter " than their original inventors. Here is possible physics behind those quantum modified general relativity equations Refs.(51-56).

We may start with noticing that universe exponential inflation happened at faster than the speed of light (superluminal speed). And original compact vacuum degrees of freedom got expanded into our space/universe beyond causal horizon, thus creating entanglements. In fact any entanglements (or even possible wormholes ER=EPR Ref.(56)) create conditions for superluminal propagation of disturbances of space-time.

And there are two interpretations of relativity principles. First, that superluminal propagation of disturbances is impossible. And second, possible, being Lorentz invariant. And Qmoger theory is fully covariant including newly added covariant divergence of space-time Refs.(51-56).

With superluminal/supercausal propagation of space-time disturbances we have longitudinal/ "compression" space-time waves (not of space itself, where only transverse waves are possible). Longitudinal waves mean compressibility of space-time and appearance of sources/sinks and creation/absorption of mass/energy and thus removing singularity of those equations and necessity for Big Bang. Still this theory is only viable in dimensions 3+1 Refs.(51-55) and only explanation of appearance of our 3D space/universe is aforementioned instability of 3D vorton collapse/inflation.

And this theory means that universe appears to be open thermodynamic system and energy and mass are not preserved, unlike in original general relativity Ref.(35). Longitudinal waves of space-time predicted there could be experimentally detected Ref.(54).

New entanglements entropy based general relativity modification theory Ref.(57) logically should provide the way to calibrate coefficient at the new additive covariant divergence term in Qmoger quantum modified general relativity equations. Somewhat similar paper on sources/sinks like singularities of space time and creation/absorption of mass/energy just appeared Ref.(58).

Introducing light speed related Mach number M for longitudinal/compression space-time waves and for isentropic (constant rate of quantum entanglements) flows we have below formula Ref.(60). In case of universe expanding with Hubble constant rate H we have as a result of equation below decay of mass/energy vacuum density at $\exp(-M^2 H^3 t)$ rate.

Mach Number Role in Compressible Flows

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V = velocity
 ρ = density

p = pressure
 M = Mach

T = temperature
 R = gas constant

a = speed of sound
 γ = specific heat ratio

Conservation of Momentum:

$$\rho V dV = - dp$$

Isentropic Flow:

$$\frac{dp}{p} = \gamma \frac{d\rho}{\rho}$$

$$dp = \gamma \frac{p}{\rho} d\rho = \gamma R T d\rho$$

$$dp = a^2 d\rho$$

Combine with Momentum:

$$\rho V dV = - a^2 d\rho$$

$$-M^2 \frac{dV}{V} = \frac{d\rho}{\rho}$$

For subsonic flow ($M < 1$), density is relatively constant

For transonic flow ($M \sim 1$), density change is nearly equal to velocity change

For supersonic flow ($M > 1$), density changes faster than the velocity
by a factor of M^2

APPENDIX SECTION 2. GALERIA OF VORTON FILAMENTS TOPOLOGICAL TRANSFORMATIONS/RECONNECTIONS FROM 1980S PUBLICATIONS

Vorton ring approaches wall at 45 degrees and turns into horse shoe vortex.

Perturbed vortex tube near the wall expels vortex ring.

Crow instability reconnections of 2 anti parallel vorton filaments.

Figure 16

Two parallel moving vorton rings merger and split in perpendicular direction Refs.[3-5]

Elliptic vorton ring split into 2 rings.